

Original Research

The Effects of Regret Aversion, Loss Aversion and Financial Literacy on Real Estate Investment Decision-Making: The Mediating Role of Risk Perception

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Abstract

This research examines factors influencing real estate investment decision-making. Specifically, it investigates how regret aversion (RA), loss aversion (LA), and financial literacy (FL) influence investors' decision-making through the mediating role of risk perception (RP). Through purposive, non-probability sampling, a survey of 283 South African real estate investors was conducted, of which 277 participants were retained for analysis after six were excluded for failing to complete the survey. The collected data were analyzed using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings indicate that regret aversion ($\beta = 0.174$, $p = 0.002$), loss aversion ($\beta = 0.213$, $p = 0.001$), and financial literacy ($\beta = 0.141$, $p = 0.025$) positively influenced risk perception. In turn, risk perception had a significant positive effect on rational investment decision-making ($\beta = 0.142$, $p = 0.026$), suggesting that both behavioral biases and financial knowledge shape investors' risk assessments, which subsequently guide more deliberate and rational investment choices. Some limitations of this study include the use of a cross-sectional design, reliance on self-reported survey data, and a sample restricted to South African investors. Future research should incorporate longitudinal or experimental designs, include diverse investor populations, and explore additional behavioral biases to strengthen generalizability and construct validity. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of how behavioral biases and financial literacy interact to influence real estate investment decision-making.

Keywords: Regret Aversion; Loss Aversion; Financial Literacy; Risk Perception; Real Estate Investment Decision-Making; Investor Behavior

Introduction

Investment decision-making in the real estate sector is a complex process influenced by both cognitive and emotional factors. Investors are often faced with uncertainty regarding future returns, market volatility, and potential losses, which can shape their decision-making strategies. Behavioral finance research has shown that psychological biases, such as regret aversion and loss aversion, can significantly influence how individuals perceive risk and make investment decisions (Tversky & Kahneman, 1992; Loomes & Sugden, 1982). At the same time, financial literacy equips investors with the knowledge and skills necessary to evaluate investment opportunities critically, interpret market information, and make rational, informed choices (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014; Van Rooij et al., 2011). Evidence suggests that higher financial literacy can mitigate

the negative effects of behavioral biases, enhancing risk perception and investment outcomes. Despite the growing interest in behavioral and cognitive determinants of investment decisions, there remains limited research examining how these factors interact in the context of real estate investment in South Africa, a market characterized by both high growth potential and considerable risk. Specifically, the interplay between behavioral biases, financial literacy, and risk perception, and their combined effect on rational investment decision-making, has received little empirical attention. This study addresses this gap by investigating how regret aversion, loss aversion, and financial literacy influence risk perception, and in turn, affect rational investment decision-making among South African real estate investors. Using a survey research design and structural equation modeling, the study seeks to provide insights into the mechanisms through which behavioral and cognitive factors shape investment behavior, offering practical implications for investors, financial advisors, and policymakers.

Literature Review

Real Estate Investment Decision-Making

Real estate investment decision-making refers to the complex cognitive and evaluative process through which individuals or institutions assess the viability and expected returns of real estate assets before allocating capital (French, 2001; Bolomope et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2023). Unlike many other financial investments, real estate is characterized by high transaction costs, low liquidity, heterogeneous asset profiles, long investment horizons, and sensitivity to local economic and regulatory conditions (Singh et al., 2023). These attributes make the decision-making process both analytically demanding and psychologically nuanced.

Classical financial theory assumes that investors are rational actors who make decisions to maximize expected utility based on available information and known risk preferences, reflecting the principles of rationality, risk aversion, and utility maximization articulated in Expected Utility Theory (von Neumann & Morgenstern, 1944). In such models, decisions are shaped by objective economic indicators such as cash flows, capitalization rates, discount rates, and expected rental yields (Singh et al., 2023). However, a substantial body of behavioral research indicates that real investors often deviate from strict rationality, especially in complex and illiquid markets like real estate.

Behavioral finance posits that cognitive biases, emotions, and heuristics influence how investors perceive and react to uncertainty (Shefrin, 2000; Barberis & Thaler, 2003). In real estate markets, where information may be incomplete or costly to obtain, these influences become particularly salient. Investors may use mental shortcuts or be swayed by past experiences, leading to decisions that diverge from classical expected utility models (Singh et al., 2023).

Risk Perception

The term risk perception refers to how investors interpret the potential risks associated with financial assets based on their personal concerns, experiences, and knowledge (Ahmad & Shah, 2020). Risk and uncertainty are closely related concepts, both of which shape the intensity and evaluation of risk as perceived by investors (Ishfaq et al., 2017). As a critical component of the decision-making process, risk perception influences the strategies investors and policymakers adopt to minimize potential losses when investing or developing projects. Investors with extensive knowledge and experience in financial markets tend to perceive risk more accurately than novice investors, who may misjudge probabilities or outcomes (Nguyen & Rozsa, 2019). Moreover, risk perception is inherently subjective, shaped by individual beliefs, judgments, and the composition of an investor's portfolio; consequently, different investors often perceive the same investment risk differently. Importantly, risk perception has a direct impact on risk-taking behavior, as higher perceived risk typically reduces an investor's willingness to engage in potentially profitable, yet uncertain, ventures (Weber et al., 2002).

Effect of Regret Aversion on Risk Perception

Regret theory, developed by Fishburn (1982), Loomes and Sugden (1982), and Bell (1982) provides a

behavioral framework for understanding how emotional responses, such as regret and joy, influence decision-making under uncertainty. Yang and Wang (2018) further emphasized that regret theory can serve as an alternative behavioral model for explaining regret aversion in financial contexts. The theory is based on two key assumptions: first, individuals frequently experience emotions such as regret and joy; and second, when making decisions under uncertainty, they anticipate and incorporate these emotional responses into their choices.

Individuals who are sensitive to regret tend to anticipate negative emotional outcomes associated with poor investment decisions. Consequently, they perceive investment options as riskier, often overestimating potential losses to avoid future regret (Loomes & Sugden, 1982). Regret-averse investors may therefore adopt more conservative strategies, avoiding investments with higher expected returns if these involve greater uncertainty. Moreover, heightened sensitivity to regret can amplify attention to past investment mistakes and influence the evaluation of new opportunities, further increasing perceived risk. However, while this bias can distort judgment, it can also encourage more deliberate, cautious, and rational decision-making, providing additional support for our hypothesis. As such, it can be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 1: *Regret aversion has a significant positive effect on risk perception.*

Effect of Financial Literacy on Risk Perception

Financial literacy is defined as the ability to make effective decisions regarding the use and management of personal financial resources (Nguyen et al., 2016). It also reflects an individual's capacity to understand and apply financial information with confidence and skill (Huston, 2010). As a critical component of economic empowerment, financial literacy is central to strategies aimed at improving the well-being of local populations (Ramalho & Forte, 2019). Conceptually, it is often viewed as a specialized form of investor knowledge, encompassing the skills necessary to manage financial affairs successfully (Alba & Hutchinson, 1987). According to Giesler and Veresiu (2014), an investor's ability to understand how money works and to use it to maximize returns is largely determined by their level of financial literacy. Individuals with higher financial literacy are better able to comprehend financial products and market dynamics, enabling them to assess financial data accurately and make informed investment decisions (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2011).

Financially literate investors are more capable of identifying sources of risk, distinguishing between systematic and unsystematic risks, and evaluating the probability and potential impact of losses. This enhanced understanding increases awareness of potential pitfalls and improves the accuracy of risk assessments, supporting more informed and rational decision-making (Nguyen et al., 2016). Additionally, financially literate individuals can integrate information from multiple sources, anticipate market fluctuations, and consider alternative investment scenarios, which reduces susceptibility to cognitive biases and overreactions to short-term volatility. Consequently, financial literacy is closely linked to an investor's ability to perceive and manage risk effectively, promoting prudent investment behavior and minimizing the likelihood of costly errors (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). As such, it can be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 2: *Financial literacy has a significant positive effect on risk perception.*

Effect of Loss Aversion on Risk Perception

Loss aversion is a central concept in behavioral economics (Blavatsky, 2024). This concept was developed by Kahneman and Tversky (1979), noting that losses are perceived as more significant than equivalent gains. Specifically, the negative emotional impact of losing a sum of money is typically stronger than the positive satisfaction of gaining the same amount. Loss aversion is a distinct construct reflecting people's desire to minimize losses and to weigh losses more heavily than proportional gains. Although it is difficult to quantify the magnitude of pain and happiness from loss and gain respectively, research suggests that losses can be twice as powerful as gains (Kahneman & Tversky, 1992). Consistent with Prospect Theory, individuals who strongly prefer avoiding losses over acquiring gains are more likely to perceive higher levels of risk when making investment decisions (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). Moreover, loss-averse investors tend to adopt more conservative strategies, avoiding investments with higher potential returns if they involve greater uncertainty. This heightened sensitivity to potential losses can amplify attention to past investment mistakes

and increase cautious evaluation of new opportunities, further elevating perceived risk. As such, it can be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 3: *Loss aversion has a significant positive effect on risk perception.*

Effect of Risk Perception on Investment Decision-Making

Individuals who perceive higher levels of risk tend to engage in more deliberate and systematic evaluation of investment options. Heightened risk perception prompts investors to process information more thoroughly, consider potential outcomes, and weigh both gains and losses before making decisions (Slovic, 1987). This careful assessment reduces impulsive behavior and promotes the adoption of strategies aimed at minimizing potential losses while optimizing returns. Research in behavioral finance suggests that risk perception not only influences the selection of assets but also affects the timing, diversification, and monitoring of investment portfolios, ultimately contributing to more rational and informed decision-making (Weber, Blais, & Betz, 2002). By contrast, individuals with lower sensitivity to risk may overlook potential pitfalls, engage in overconfident investment behaviors, or adopt high-risk strategies without adequate consideration of negative consequences. Given this relationship, it can be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 4: *Risk perception has a significant positive effect on rational investment decision-making.*

Fig. 1: Theoretical Model

Materials and Methods

A survey research design was utilized to examine the effects of regret aversion, loss aversion and financial literacy on real estate investment decision-making as mediated by risk perception. Having obtained ethical approval from relevant authorities, I relied on a purposive nonprobability sampling to recruit 283 investors in South Africa. To recruit these participants, I developed a recruitment advertisement and posted it on Facebook, across six real estate development groups that included South African real estate developers and investors. The written advertisement reiterated the main purpose of the study, indicated the eligibility criteria, and explained the uncompensated and voluntary nature of participation. Only South African real estate investors aged 18 years and above were eligible to participate in the study.

The recruitment advertisement had a survey link that directed interested candidates to an online consent form, followed by the linked survey questionnaire. The researcher's developed consent form explained the main objectives of the study, procedures, participation criteria, anonymity safeguards and the voluntary nature of the study. Participants were advised not to provide any identifying personal information, such as names or addresses, to safeguard their privacy and confidentiality. The screening questions were designed in such a manner that they excluded non South African real estate investors and anyone below 18 years. The

survey questionnaire was hosted on SurveyMonkey, and data collection took place over a period of two-weeks. Only participants who met the eligibility criteria and provided informed consent were allowed to complete the survey questionnaire. The survey questions (Table 1) were based on the following measures:

Table 1: Measurements

Construct	Number of Items	Items (5-point Likert, Ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree)
Regret Aversion	5	I prefer to keep current investments rather than switch to alternatives with higher potential returns.
		I avoid repeating past investment mistakes.
		Previous losses make me hesitant in new investment decisions.
		I anticipate regret when considering risky investments.
		Fear of regret influences how I evaluate investments.
Loss Aversion	5	Losing money feels worse than gaining the same amount feels good.
		I dislike selling at a loss more than enjoy selling at a gain.
		I focus more on potential losses than gains.
		Even small loss risks influence my decisions.
		I am more motivated to avoid losses than to achieve gains.
Financial Literacy	5	I understand how interest rates affect investment returns.
		I am confident choosing among financial products.
		I can calculate inflation's impact on savings.
		I understand diversification and risk reduction.
		I can interpret basic financial statements.
Rational Investment Decision-Making (RIDM)	5	I base investment decisions on careful analysis rather than emotions.
		I evaluate multiple scenarios before investing.
		I consider long-term outcomes.
		I incorporate risk assessment into decisions.
		I avoid impulsive investment decisions.
Risk Perception	5	I perceive investing in stocks as risky.
		I believe financial markets are unpredictable.
		I feel there is high uncertainty in investment returns.
		Potential losses influence how risky I view options.
		I am concerned about risks in long-term investing.

Data Analysis and Results

Descriptive Statistics

Of the 283 participants initially recruited, 277 were retained for analysis, as six were excluded for failing to complete the survey.

Table 2: Gender of Participants

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	143	51.6	51.6
Female	134	48.4	100
Total	277	100	

Table 2 shows the gender distribution of participants, indicating a nearly balanced sample with 51.6% male and 48.4% female respondents.

Table 3: Participants' Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
20 years and below	17	6.1	6.1
21 to 30 years	185	66.8	72.9
31 to 40 years	72	26	98.9
41 to 50 years	3	1.1	100
Total	277	100	

Table 3 presents the age distribution of participants, showing that the majority (66.8%) are between 21 and 30 years, followed by 26% aged 31 to 40 years. Only a small proportion are 20 years and below (6.1%) or 41 to 50 years (1.1%).

Table 4: Participants' Level of Education

Education	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
High School	20	7.2	7.2	7.2
Diploma	74	26.7	26.7	33.9
Bachelors Degree	178	64.3	64.3	98.2
Masters Degree	5	1.8	1.8	100
Total	277	100	100	

Employment

The distribution of participants' work experience indicates that the majority (76.9%) have five years or less of experience, followed by 12.3% with six to ten years. Only a small proportion reported 11 to 15 years (1.8%) and 16 to 20 years (1.4%) of experience, while 7.6% were unemployed.

Construct Reliability and Validity

Table 5: Construct Reliability and Validity

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (rho_a)	Composite Reliability (rho_c)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Financial Literacy	0.769	0.862	0.827	0.508
Loss Aversion	0.870	0.894	0.904	0.653
RIDM	0.847	0.890	0.888	0.615
Regret Aversion	0.818	0.901	0.867	0.568
Risk Perception	0.901	0.917	0.926	0.715

Table 5 presents the assessment of internal consistency reliability and convergent validity for the study constructs, indicating that the measurement model is both reliable and valid. All constructs exhibit Cronbach's alpha values above the recommended threshold of 0.70, ranging from 0.769 for financial literacy to 0.901 for risk perception, demonstrating satisfactory internal consistency (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). This is further supported by composite reliability values (rho_a, and rho_c), which exceed the acceptable level of 0.70 across all constructs, confirming the robustness and consistency of the measurement items (Hair et al., 2019). In terms of convergent validity, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs surpass the minimum threshold of 0.50, with values ranging from 0.508 to 0.715, indicating that each construct

explains a substantial proportion of variance in its indicators (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 6: Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

Construct	Financial Literacy	Loss Aversion	RIDM	Regret Aversion
Loss Aversion	0.346			
RIDM	0.779	0.213		
Regret Aversion	0.341	0.144	0.187	
Risk Perception	0.257	0.290	0.152	0.235

Table 6 presents the discriminant validity assessment based on the HTMT criterion. All inter-construct HTMT values fall below the recommended threshold of 0.85 (Henseler et al., 2015), indicating that the constructs are empirically distinct. The highest observed value, 0.779 between financial literacy and rational investment decision-making, remains below the cutoff, while all other values range from 0.144 to 0.346, confirming that loss aversion, regret aversion, and risk perception represent theoretically and empirically separate constructs. These findings provide robust evidence of discriminant validity, ensuring that the measurement model is suitable for structural analysis.

Table 7: Fornell Lacker Criterion

Construct	Financial Literacy	Loss Aversion	RIDM	Regret Aversion	Risk Perception
Financial Literacy	0.713				
Loss Aversion	0.303	0.808			
RIDM	0.442	0.183	0.784		
Regret Aversion	0.260	0.117	0.150	0.754	
Risk Perception	0.251	0.277	0.142	0.235	0.846

Table 7 presents the assessment of discriminant validity using the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The square roots of the AVE for all constructs (diagonal values) exceed their correlations with other constructs, indicating that each construct shares more variance with its indicators than with any other construct (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). These results provide further evidence of discriminant validity and confirm that the constructs are empirically distinct, supporting the adequacy of the measurement model for subsequent structural analysis.

Hypotheses Testing

Figure 2: PLS Algorithm

Table 8: Pearson Correlations

Construct	LA	FL	RP	RA	RIDM
LA	1				
FL	.278**	1			
RP	.257**	.211**	1		
RA	.119*	.268**	.200**	1	
RIDM	.179**	.636**	.133*	.150*	1
N	277				
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).					

Table 8 shows the Pearson correlation coefficients among the study constructs. Based on the results, all variables are positively and significantly correlated, providing preliminary support for the hypothesized relationships. Risk perception is positively associated with loss aversion ($r = 0.257$), financial literacy ($r = 0.211$), and regret aversion ($r = 0.200$), suggesting that both behavioral biases and financial literacy influence how individuals perceive risk. In addition, rational investment decision-making is positively associated with financial literacy ($r = 0.636$). Rational investment decision-making is also positively associated with loss aversion ($r = 0.179$), regret aversion ($r = 0.150$), and risk perception ($r = 0.133$).

Figure 3: Bootstrapping

Table 9: Hypotheses Testing Results

Model Path	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T statistics	P values	Decision
Regret Aversion -> Risk Perception	0.174	0.184	0.056	3.127	0.002	Positive
Financial Literacy -> Risk Perception	0.141	0.154	0.063	2.247	0.025	Positive
Loss Aversion -> Risk Perception	0.213	0.216	0.066	3.232	0.001	Positive
Risk Perception -> RIDM	0.142	0.163	0.064	2.228	0.026	Positive

Table 9 and Figure 3 show the structural equation model results and hypothesis testing. All hypothesized paths were positive and statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Specifically, Regret Aversion ($\beta = 0.174$, $t = 3.127$, $p = 0.002$), Loss Aversion ($\beta = 0.213$, $t = 3.232$, $p = 0.001$), and Financial Literacy ($\beta = 0.141$, $t = 2.247$, $p = 0.025$) each had a significant positive effect on Risk Perception. In turn, Risk Perception exhibited a significant

positive effect on Rational Investment Decision-Making (RIDM) ($\beta = 0.142$, $t = 2.228$, $p = 0.026$). These results provide empirical support for the proposed model, confirming that both behavioral biases and financial literacy influence risk perception, which subsequently affects rational investment decisions.

Table 10: Post-Hoc Power Analysis

Model Path	Path coefficients	Alpha 1%	Alpha 5%
Financial Literacy -> Risk Perception	0.141	0.511	0.761
Loss Aversion -> Risk Perception	0.213	0.89	0.972
Regret Aversion -> Risk Perception	0.174	0.714	0.894
Risk Perception -> RIDM	0.142	0.517	0.765

Table 10 presents the results of the post-hoc power

analysis for the structural model paths. Statistical power was assessed at both 1% and 5% significance levels to evaluate the likelihood of detecting the observed effects. The analysis shows that all paths achieved adequate power, particularly at the 5% level. Even at the more conservative 1% level, power values exceed 0.50, indicating a reasonable probability of correctly rejecting the null hypothesis. These results suggest that the sample size and effect sizes are sufficient to support the reliability of the structural path estimates and reduce the risk of Type II errors in the model.

Results Discussions

The results of this study suggest that regret aversion has a positive and statistically significant effect on risk perception. This shows that investors who anticipate regret from unfavorable real estate investment outcomes are more likely to perceive higher levels of risk when making investment decisions. This anticipation of future regret enhances sensitivity to potential negative outcomes, thereby influencing more cautious evaluations of investment opportunities. This finding aligns with the regret theory, which entails that individuals incorporate anticipated emotional consequences into their decision-making processes, often resulting in more conservative judgments under uncertainty (Loomes & Sugden, 1982; Zeelenberg, 1999).

Furthermore, the results indicate that loss aversion has a positive and significant effect on risk perception. This shows that investors who are more sensitive to losses than gains have a tendency of interpreting investment situations as inherently riskier. This result is consistent with the Prospect Theory, which entails that loss-averse individuals tend to focus more on the downside risks, thereby heightening the levels of perceived uncertainty (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). However, while this bias can distort judgment, it can also influence more deliberate, cautious and rational decision-making, providing support for our hypotheses. The results further shows that financial literacy has a positive and statistically significant effect on risk perception. This suggest that individuals with enormous financial knowledge are well equipped to essentially recognize and assess investment risks. Instead of minimizing the perceived risk, financial literacy enhances awareness and critical evaluation of financial risks and uncertainties. This echoes prior research suggesting that financially literate investors have the ability to process complex information and make informed judgments regarding investment risks (Van Rooij et al., 2011; Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014).

In turn, the results suggest that risk perception has a positive and significant effect on rational investment decision-making. This shows that a more refined and better understanding of investment risks is associated with rational and deliberate investment choices. Real estate investors who accurately anticipate risks are more likely to engage in careful analysis and avoid impulsive decisions. This aligns with prior studies emphasizing the key role of risk perception in shaping decision quality and behavioral outcomes in financial contexts (Sitkin & Weingart, 1995; Weber et al., 2002). As such, the results of this study confirm that regret aversion, loss aversion and financial literacy have a positive and significant effect on risk perception, which in turn influences rational real estate investment decision-making. Hence, all proposed hypotheses are supported.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

One of the key limitations is that this study relied on a purposive non-probability sampling technique, which

essentially limits the generalizability of the findings. Since the research participants were recruited through Facebook real estate groups, the sample could have overrepresented younger participants who are tech-savvy and more active online investors, as shown by the age distribution where 66.8% of respondents were between 21 and 30 years. This sampling approach likely could have excluded older or less digitally engaged investors, potentially contributing to biased results.

In addition, the self-reported nature of the survey data is another limitation, which introduces the potential for social desirability bias and response bias. Participants of this study may have given responses that reflect how they perceive they should behave as investors rather than their actual decision-making behavior.

Moreover, due to the reliance on a cross-sectional survey, it is not possible to infer causal relationships definitively between regret aversion, loss aversion, financial literacy, risk perception, and rational investment decision-making since data were collected at a single point in time. In addition, this study is geographically and contextually limited to South African real estate investors, which may affect the external validity of the findings. Although structural equation modeling provides evidence of statistical associations, future studies could also employ longitudinal and experimental designs to cater for temporal precedence and causal inference. Future studies should also conduct comparative research across different geographical locations to examine whether the relationships observed in this study hold in other cultural, economic, and regulatory contexts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several practical recommendations can be made for real estate investors and financial advisors. First, investors should engage in awareness and training programs to better understand how behavioral biases, such as regret aversion and loss aversion, influence their risk perception and investment decisions. By recognizing these biases, investors can adopt strategies to mitigate emotional decision-making, such as using structured decision frameworks or checklists when evaluating investment opportunities.

Second, given the positive role of financial literacy in enhancing risk perception, investors are encouraged to improve their financial knowledge through courses, workshops, and professional advice. This can enable them to critically assess investment risks and make more rational, deliberate decisions, reducing impulsive or overly cautious behavior.

Third, financial institutions and real estate advisory firms should consider tailoring investment guidance based on individual investor profiles, including their risk tolerance, experience level, and susceptibility to behavioral biases. Personalized advice can help investors balance potential gains and losses more effectively while promoting sustainable investment practices.

Moreover, for policymakers and educators, integrating financial literacy programs into broader educational initiatives can cultivate a more informed investor population, enhancing overall market stability and efficiency.

Conclusion

This study examined the effects of regret aversion, loss aversion, and financial literacy on real estate investment decision-making, as mediated by risk perception, among South African investors. The results indicate that both behavioral biases and financial literacy significantly influence how investors perceive risk, which in turn affects their rational investment decisions. Specifically, investors who anticipate regret, are sensitive to losses, or possess higher financial literacy tend to perceive higher levels of risk and make more deliberate and rational investment choices.

Despite the study's limitations, such as reliance on self-reported survey data and a geographically limited sample, the findings contribute valuable insights into the psychological and cognitive factors underlying real estate investment behavior. The study highlights the importance of addressing behavioral biases and promoting financial literacy to enhance investment decision quality. Future research can build on these findings by incorporating behavioral experiments, longitudinal tracking, and cross-cultural comparisons to deepen understanding of investor decision-making in diverse contexts.

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